

Formation Constants of Mixed-Ligand Complexes of Oxovanadium(IV) with Some Dicarboxylic Acids and Pyridine-2-aldoxime

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Oxovanadium(IV) has been shown to form mixed-ligand complexes, MAL and MAL(OH) (where $M=VO^{2+}$; H_2A =oxalic, phthalic and maleic acids and HL=pyridine-2-aldoxime) from the pH-metric titration curves in the ternary systems, VO^{2+} -dicarboxylic acids-pyridine-2-aldoxime. The formation constants of the mixed-ligand complexes, MAL have been determined at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ ($\mu=0.1$ KNO₃).

PYRIDINE-2-aldoxime has been shown in the recent past¹ to form only monohydroxo derivative, VO(OH)A with oxovanadium(IV) by pH-metric method and the equilibrium constant for the reaction $VO^{2+} + H_2A^+ + H_2O \rightleftharpoons VO(OH)A + 3H^+$ (where H_2A^+ =pyridine-2-aldoxime hydrochloride) reported. The formation constants of the resulting complexes in the simple binary systems, VO^{2+} -oxalic acid/phthalic acid/maleic acid and ternary complexes with oxalic, phthalic and maleic acids as one of the ligands have also been reported^{2-4,6}. Such studies have now been extended to other ternary systems, VO^{2+} -oxalic acid/phthalic acid/maleic acid-pyridine-2-aldoxime and the results are presented in this paper.

Experimental

A stock solution of vanadyl sulphate(BDH) was prepared in doubly distilled water and standardized against disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid using 7-phenylazo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid as an indicator⁵. Pyridine-2-aldoxime (Fluka purum), oxalic (BDH AnalaR), phthalic (BDH), maleic (Burgoyne) acids were prepared by direct weighing and standardized potentiometrically against potassium hydroxide (0.1M). The pH-titrations were carried out at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ with a Cambridge pH-meter standardized against 0.05M solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate. The volume of solutions to be titrated was always kept constant (50 ml) by mixing with the requisite volume of doubly distilled water; the ionic strength was maintained constant ($\mu=0.1$ KNO₃) by adding 5.0 ml of 1.0 M KNO₃ to each solution and titrated against standard KOH solution.

Results and Discussion

The potentiometric titration curves of oxalic, phthalic and maleic acids; pyridine-2-aldoxime and vanadyl sulphate in presence of an equimolar concentration of these ligands have been described earlier^{6,1} and the calculations of the acid dissociation constants (k_1 and k_2) of ligands; equilibrium (K_1) and stability (K_{MA}) constants of 1:1 chelates and hydrolysis constants of monohydroxo derivatives of 1:1 chelates have also been reported (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS AND EQUILIBRIUM, FORMATION AND HYDROLYSIS CONSTANTS OF 1:1 CHELATES ($t=30^\circ$)

Ligand	pK_1	pK_2	$-\log K_1$	$\log K_{MA}$	$-\log K_H$
Oxalic acid	1.66	3.90	0.91	4.65	4.49
Phthalic acid	2.89	5.04	3.92	4.01	8.47
Maleic acid	2.28	5.97	3.79	4.41	8.53
Pyridine-2-aldoxime	3.78	9.84	—	—	8.40

Curves 9-11 (Fig. 1) represent the potentiometric titrations of vanadyl sulphate in presence of equimolar concentrations of one of the primary ligands (H_2A =oxalic, phthalic and maleic acids) and pyridine-2-aldoxime (H_2L^+). In the initial stage, all these curves superimpose over the corresponding 1:1 VO^{2+} -oxalic acid/phthalic acid/maleic acid systems (curves 5-7; Fig. 1) and the lowering of these curves, which is a measure of mixed-ligand chelate formation, occurs after $m=1.2$, 0.2 and 0.4 in case of VO^{2+} -oxalic acid/phthalic acid/maleic acid-pyridine-2-aldoxime systems (m represents the moles of base added per mole of

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Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves of mixed-ligand chelates; VO(IV)-Oxalic acid/phthalic acid/maleic acid-pyridine-2-aldoxime: 1, Oxalic acid; 2, Phthalic acid; 3, Maleic acid; 4, Pyridine-2-aldoxime; 5, 6, 7 & 8, VO(IV)-Oxalic acid/Phthalic acid/Maleic acid/Pyridine-2-aldoxime (1 : 1); 9, 10 & 11 VO(IV)-Oxalic acid/Phthalic acid/Maleic acid-Pyridine-2-aldoxime (1 : 1 : 1). Arrow indicates the appearance of solid phase.

metal or ligand ions). This indicates that initially a VO²⁺-oxalic acid, phthalic acid or maleic acid (1 : 1) complex is formed in the above systems. Further, the lowering of these curves in comparison to the corresponding composite curves (which can be drawn by adding the horizontal distance of the secondary ligand curve to the horizontal distance of the VO²⁺-oxalic acid/phthalic acid/maleic acid curve at the same pH) inferred the formation of mixed-ligand chelates in the ternary systems. Thus the formation of the ternary complexes takes place in overlapping steps and through the formation of 1 : 1 chelates with primary ligands.

Further, poor inflections at m=4 followed by another inflection at m=5 in case of VO²⁺-oxalic acid/maleic acid-pyridine-2-aldoxime and only one inflection at m=5 in case of VO²⁺-phthalic acid-pyridine-2-aldoxime indicate the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed-ligand chelate species, VOAL⁻ and its conversion into hydroxo derivatives in overlapping steps. The formation of ternary chelates is also supported by the analysis of the potentiometric data given below :

Assuming the absence of the species VOAL₂²⁻, VOAL₃³⁻, etc., when the ratio of metal ion to ligands is 1 : 1 : 1 and the formation of only mononuclear

metal chelate species, the equilibria involved in the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed-ligand complexes in the above systems, may be represented as :

and the overall reaction for the formation of the mixed-ligand chelate may be shown as :

In the pH-range studied before the precipitation starts, neglecting the concentration of OH⁻, L⁻ and hydrolyzed species of vanadyl ions as compared with those of other species present in the equilibrium mixture, the following equations are obtained for maintaining the material balance :

$$T_M = [\text{VO}^{2+}] + [\text{VOA}] + [\text{VOAL}^-] \quad \dots \text{(1)}$$

$$T_{OH} + [\text{H}^+] = 2[\text{VOA}] + 4[\text{VOAL}^-] + [\text{HA}^-] + 2[\text{A}^{2-}] + [\text{HL}] \quad \dots \text{(2)}$$

$$T_A = [\text{H}_2\text{A}] + [\text{HA}] + [\text{A}^{2-}] + [\text{VOA}] + [\text{VOAL}^-] \quad \dots \text{(3)}$$

$$T_L = [\text{H}_2\text{L}^+] + [\text{HL}] + [\text{VOAL}^-] \quad \dots \text{(4)}$$

where T_M, T_A and T_L represent the total concentrations of metal, primary and secondary ligand species respectively and T_{OH} is the concentration of the base added to the reaction mixture during the titration. The hydrolysis of 1 : 1 VO²⁺-oxalic acid/phthalic acid/maleic acid chelate VOA were also considered to be negligible in presence of the secondary ligand.

In a 1 : 1 : 1 reaction mixture, using the equations (1)-(4) and relations for the dissociation constants of ligands and equilibrium constant (K₁) of the reaction : VO²⁺ + H₂A ⇌ VOA + 2H⁺, it may be shown that :

$$a[\text{VO}^{2+}]^2 + b[\text{VO}^{2+}] - c = 0 \quad \dots \text{(5)}$$

$$\text{where, } a = \left(2 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]}\right) \frac{K_1}{[\text{H}^+]^2},$$

$$b = 2xy + \left(1 - \frac{k_1 k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2}\right) y + x,$$

$$c = \{(4 - m) T_M - [\text{H}^+]\} xy$$

$$x = \left(1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]}\right) + \frac{k_1 k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2}, \quad y = \left(1 + \frac{k'_1}{[\text{H}^+]}\right)$$

k₁ and k₂ are the dissociation constant of the dicarboxylic acid and k'₁ the first dissociation constant of pyridine-2-aldoxime. The equilibrium concentration of the free vanadyl ions present in the reaction mixture at various points of titration curves for ternary systems was obtained by solving equation (5). The concentrations of other species involved in the equilibrium relations was then calculated from the above equations and also the values of equilibrium constants K' and K'' of the reactions (i) and (ii) respectively.

Stability constants of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed-ligand chelates : The stability constant of the ternary com-

plex which may be defined as

$$K_{MAL} = \frac{[VOAL^-]}{[VOA][L^-]}$$

was determined by the expression :

$$K_{MAL} = \frac{K'}{k'_1 k'_2} \quad \dots (6)$$

where k'_1 and k'_2 are the dissociation constants of the secondary ligand.

The overall stability constant of the mixed-ligand chelate

$$\beta_{MAL} = \frac{[VOAL^-]}{[VO^{2+}][A^{2-}][L^-]}$$

was calculated by the expression

$$\beta_{MAL} = \frac{K''}{k_1 k_2 k'_1 k'_2} \quad \dots (7)$$

Constant values of the equilibrium and stability constants have been obtained at all points of titration curves before the precipitation occurs at about $m=3.2$, 2.4 and 2.2 in the systems VO^{2+} -oxalic acid/phthalic acid/maleic acid—pyridine-2-aldoxime respectively. The values are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM AND CHELATE FORMATION CONSTANTS OF MIXED-LIGAND CHELATES				
Systems	$-\log K'$	$-\log K''$	$\log K_{MAL}$	$\log \beta_{MAL}$
VO^{2+} -Oxalic acid-pyridine-2-aldoxime	5.39 ± 0.13	6.30 ± 0.13	8.18 ± 0.13	12.83 ± 0.13
VO^{2+} -Phthalic acid-pyridine-2-aldoxime	4.95 ± 0.03	8.87 ± 0.03	8.62 ± 0.03	12.63 ± 0.03
VO^{2+} -Maleic acid-pyridine-2-aldoxime	4.33 ± 0.12	8.12 ± 0.12	9.24 ± 0.12	13.65 ± 0.12

Although the formation of hydroxo derivatives of 1:1:1 mixed-ligand complexes have been inferred on the basis of the titration curves, the values of the formation constants for these complexes could not be calculated due to the appearance of a solid phase at an early stage.

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